

A NOTE ON THE OCCURRENCE OF FREE FATTY ACIDS IN THE CAKE OF *PONGAMIA GLABRA*.

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The seed-cake of *Pongamia glabra* has been recommended by Desai Sudborough and Watson (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1923, 6, 93) as a good manure owing to its high nitrogen content. Later Srinivasan and Subrahmanyan (*ibid.*, 1934, 17, 49) isolated a protein from the seed-cake using sodium carbonate solution as solvent. They have found use for this protein in the preparation of water paints. Apart from this, no systematic study of the seed-cake seems to have been made.

The seed-cake, obtained by pressing out the oil from the seeds in a country press, was extracted with petroleum ether and the extract on concentration yielded a colourless waxy substance (0.7%). On close examination it was found to be a mixture and one of the components could be easily separated on account of its sparing solubility in hot petroleum ether. This product could be identified as karanjin from its well known properties. The petroleum ether-soluble fraction yielded a waxy substance, which melted at 73.5-75°. The acid number and saponification value (162.0 and 162.4 respectively) of the substance agreed very closely, thereby showing that it consists mostly of fatty acids. The iodine number of the product was very low indicating that the acids were highly saturated. On saponification and extraction of the dry soap with petrol very little non-saponifiable matter was obtained and the mixed fatty acids liberated from the soap exhibited the same properties as the original substance. It is interesting to note that the seed-cake of *Pongamia glabra* yields almost completely saturated fatty acids having a mean molecular weight of 345.5.

The fatty acids obtained have been small in amount and, therefore, a regular separation of the components by the fractionation method could not be effected. The melting point, saponification equivalent and iodine number indicate the acids to belong to saturated higher fatty acids above stearic in the series. The mixture of fatty acids is readily soluble in ether at the laboratory temperature and at 16° 0.5 g. of it dissolves in 30 c.c. of ether (behenic acid has very low solubility—0.19 g. in 100 c.c. of ether at 16°, whereas arachidic and lignoceric acids are readily soluble

in ether). Attempts made to effect the separation of the acids either by fractional crystallisation or through their salts were not successful. From the available data, the mixture appears to consist primarily of arachidic and lignoceric acids. In view of the fact that arachidic, behenic and lignoceric acids have been reported to be present in the oil (Manjunath and Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **15**, 653) the mixture may contain behenic acid also but this must be only in a very small amount.

The isolation of these fatty acids from the seed-cake offers an explanation of the results obtained by previous workers on the expelled oil (Desai *et al*, *loc. cit.*) and solvent-extracted oil (Grimme, *Chem. Rev.*, 1910, **17**, 233). The results are tabulated below.

	Properties of mixed fatty acids							
	Acid value.	Sap. value.	I V.	Titre test.	M.p.	Neut. value	I. V.	Mean M.W.
Expelled oil	6.4	185.7	88.9	29.5		191.8	91.2	292.5
Ether-extracted oil	42.3	185.1	77.3	42.5	43.8	180.1	78.8	308.7

The ether-extracted oil obviously brings along with it these saturated higher fatty acids (free) due to which it has a higher acid value and lower iodine value. The mixed fatty acids liberated from it have a higher melting point and higher mean molecular weight than those obtained from the expelled oil. Further, this oil has been observed on keeping for a week or two to deposit these solid fatty acids admixed with a little karanjin (Rao and Seshadri, *Current Sci.*, 1940, **4** 76), whereas the expelled oil did not do so during the same time.

The results described above definitely indicate the occurrence of saturated higher fatty acids (free) in the seed, their retention largely by the cake when the oil is pressed out and their presence in the oil when it is obtained by solvent extraction.

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